

SHAPE Project Shiloh Industries Italia

Multiphasic Simulation in High-Pressure Die Casting Process

Bernardo Puddu^{*a}, Raffaele Ponzini^b, Davide Garetto^a

^a *Shiloh Industries Italia, Verres, Italy*

^b *CINECA, Milan, Italy*

Abstract

Shiloh Industries Italia s.r.l. has been working in the market of casted components since 1992 updating manufacturing activities to novel standards imposed by continuous technological improvement. At the moment Shiloh is using standard software to develop new products and support production requirements. The adoption of CFD tools is a mandatory task today when trying to perform daily numerical modelling activities to support production needs with standard commercial ISV applications. Nevertheless, the adopted software workflow does not contain a multiphasic solver, thus it is difficult to analyse in a quantitative way the air entrapment volumes identifying bubble sizes. The present project's main aim is to test a state-of-the-art HPC infrastructure and open-source technologies to evaluate possible benefits on cost, time-to-results for the single design, and number of achieved designs per day in a multiphasic simulation. A preliminary well-known reference case study will be evaluated to assess the possibility to implement relevant physical parameters into the computational model. Scalability of the CFD solver and automation of the overall identified workflow will also be tested in order to evaluate the portability to Shiloh's present way of working.

1. Introduction

Shiloh Industries Italia s.r.l (Shiloh) has been working in the market of casted components since 1992 updating manufacturing activities to novel standards imposed by continuous technological improvement. Since December 2015, Shiloh has been using standard software to develop new products and support production requirements. The adoption of CFD tools is a mandatory task within Shiloh's workflow. Shiloh performs daily numerical modelling activities and today is working with standard commercial ISV application to develop in-house CFD models necessary to perform preliminary assessment and final verification of different product and process designs. Nevertheless, the adopted software workflow does not contain a multiphasic solver, thus it is difficult to analyse in a quantitative way the air entrapment volumes identifying bubble sizes. The computations are performed using a single state-of-the-art desktop computer made up of only 16 computational cores. This limits the time-to-results and the number of configurations analysed in a working day. The company has no direct experience up to now of using HPC infrastructures, or open-source CFD toolkits.

In synthesis, the present limitations of the actual adopted application workflow are:

- the lack of a quantitative gas phase evaluation;
- the number of licences limited by licensing costs;
- the computational cores availability limited by the lack of experience on parallel infrastructures.

The casted components quality problems related to air bubble entrapments are crucial for Shiloh's working activities. For this reason Shiloh needs to investigate further into the multiphasic simulation process including an explicit way to simulate the gas

* Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* Bernardo.Puddu@shiloh.com

phase. Shiloh is looking to improve the knowledge of some key parameters:

- the air bubbles entrapment results to evaluate process issues;
- the time-to-results for the single design analysis;
- the number of achieved designs per day;
- the costs per single design analysis.

Simulating more, in less time and at lower cost, is becoming mandatory in the present market and Shiloh’s interest is to test how mature are open source technological solutions to help overcoming the above-mentioned limitations of the present way of working. Moreover, evaluating the possibility of performing heavy CFD computations on a pay-per-use cloud-based business model is also very attractive for Shiloh’s numerical modelling activities. The final step of testing the automation of a novel workflow is really attractive for Shiloh to streamline and standardise the computational activities. The present project’s main aim was to test a state-of-the-art HPC infrastructure and open-source technologies (OpenFOAM, see [2]) to evaluate possible benefits on cost, time-to-results for the single design, and number of achieved designs per day in a multiphase simulation. A preliminary well-known reference case study will be evaluated to assess the possibility to implement relevant physical parameters into the computational model. Scalability of the CFD solver and automation of the overall identified workflow will also be tested in order to evaluate the portability to Shiloh present way of working.

2. Methods

2.1. CFD modelling and meshing

Shiloh selected a well-known reference geometry of the die casting process. In figure 1 the CAD geometry elements are shown. The inlet is a moving wall that by advancing in its path is pushing a biphasic fluid made of air and the molten metal. There is a complex balance between the fill level and the piston velocity that must be regulated in order to avoid bubble formation and trapping into the fluid that once pushed into the stamp can represent holes that are considered as material defects.

Fig. 1. Real geometry of the injecting die casting process.

In order to study this case the reference geometry has been simplified as shown in figure 2 where also the selected fill level is shown. The main characteristic that Shiloh want to preserve in this CFD model is the possibility of having a piston as inlet of the model that moves with a constant velocity into the fluid domain pushing and squeezing the two phases into the model outlet. For Shiloh this is representative of the actual physical problem of die casting kinematics.

The reference simplified geometry has been meshed using the standard OpenFOAM meshing utilities taking care of capturing the free-surface zone with sufficient spatial accuracy since that will be the most relevant zone into the numerical model. In our reference case the final mesh was about 4 million cells with a spatial accuracy of about 0.4 mm at the free-surface zone as shown in figure 3.

In order to start getting a first insight into the interaction between the two fluids under the action of the advancing inlet boundary into the fluid domain, Shiloh decided to model the physics of the problem considering the two fluids as immiscible, incompressible and Newtonian. This is a very strong simplification, particularly concerning the absence of the heat exchanges between the two phases that is indeed a relevant component of the real physical problem. The two fluids instead have rheological properties that mimic the properties of the molten metal and of the air at a given temperature. Under these working hypotheses, the *interDyMFoam* solver can be used to represent the interactions of the two fluids including bubble formation and tracking when the inlet boundary is moving into the fluid domain. The inlet is allowed to move squeezing up to 90% of the total domain length.

Fig. 2. Simplified geometry starting two-phase condition.

Fig. 3. Simplified geometry reference mesh.

2.2. Tested conditions

In table 1 we have listed the three tested piston velocity values. Shiloh has provided these values as they are the extrema values of their working activity in die casting processing. Notably the fill level has been considered as fixed in all the tested conditions to start looking at the effect of the inlet piston velocity on the overall air bubble formation and encapsulation into the fluid.

Table 1. Fluid dynamics conditions

Test Name	Piston Velocity [m/s]
Slow	0.22
Mid	0.7
Fast	1.0

2.3. Data sampling and processing

For the three selected conditions we ran the selected solver and we monitored the isosurface at alpha equal to 0.5 (phases interface) sampling its value every 0.001 seconds. Then we processed each isosurface calculating the volume of each bubble. Finally we sampled the bubbles into 10 ‘buckets’ defined by the bubble size as follows:

1-100 mm³; 100-200 mm³; ...; 900-1000 mm³.

In order to quantify bubble volume values, even if perfect spherical bubbles are not present, we can approximate the volume using different approaches for instance defining the volume as:

$$V_{bubble} = \frac{4}{3} \pi dx * dy * dz \tag{1}$$

where dx , dy , dz are the bounding box limits in the three directions xyz of the single bubble. In figure 4 an example of a 2 mm diameter bubble is shown.

Fig. 4. Detail of a 2 mm diameter air bubble.

2.4. Scalability performance

One of the key points in the project was the time-to-result benefits obtainable thanks to the HPC infrastructure deployed by means of the open-source selected workflow. Testing the scalability of the present OpenFOAM solver, we found that to keep an

efficiency greater than 0.75 the ratio between the mesh cell number and the used computational cores needs not to be lower than about 35.000. In our test case, the mesh size was about 4 million cells and we completed the computations in 8-12 hours on CINECA's HPC Tier-1 hardware facility (see [3]) depending on the piston velocity value.

3. Results

3.1. Qualitative results

Thanks to the presented workflow, we are now able to perform different piston velocity analysis showing very different bubble entrapment patterns. In figure 5 the qualitative analysis of the free surface is shown. Slow piston velocity does not show relevant bubble formation and successive entrapment whereas the high velocity piston scenario is showing a relevant bubble formation and entrapment.

Fig. 5. (left) slow piston velocity qualitative bubble measurement; (right) fast piston velocity qualitative bubble measurement.

3.2. Quantitative results

Thanks to the presented workflow, implemented for this project, we are able also to quantify the changes in bubble formation in the injected biphasic fluid. In figure 6 it is possible to understand how different are the bubble counts for the two simulated scenarios. Nevertheless, it is important to underline that the bubble formation is not important for die casting processing, unless they get entrapped into the fluid phase, pushed into the stamp introducing faults and gaps into the final manufactured material.

Fig. 6. (left) slow piston velocity quantitative bubble measurement; (right) fast piston velocity quantitative bubble measurement.

4. Discussion and conclusions

The proposed workflow implementation has been shown to be effective under the selected working hypothesis to represent the interaction between two Newtonian fluids that share the main rheological properties with air and molten metal as in the real physical problem. We performed biphasic CFD simulations with a moving inlet that behaves like a piston pushing the two fluids into the stamp analysing the effect of different piston velocities.

We found that similar bubble bucket counting patterns are present in configurations with similar piston velocity (fast) while very different bubble buckets pattern were found in rapidly changing piston velocity (slow).

Further implementation including the effect of heat exchange between the fluids are to be considered in order to compare real physical problem with the numerical one.

References

- [1] Shiloh Industries Italia web site: <https://shiloh.com/>
- [2] OpenFOAM web site: <http://www.cfd-direct.com>.
- [3] HPC used hardware: <https://www.cineca.it/it/content/galileo>

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 730913. The work is achieved using the PRACE Research Infrastructure resources *galileo* cluster at CINECA, Italy.